

acid) are formed during first hour of oxidation. However, for samples collected at 3 hours onward the intensities of both the above mentioned peaks increase simultaneously. It suggests that attainment of almost constant acid values at 11-12 hours of oxidation is not, at least, due to exhausting of alkylhydroperoxide intermediate which is believed to take active part² in the chain-initiation and chainpropagation steps in these reactions.

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Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part XII*

Synthesis of γ -Pyrone Derivatives from 2, 4-Diacetyl Resorcinol

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IN continuation of our previous work¹ we have now studied the synthesis of γ -pyrone derivatives from 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol². On condensation with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide it gave the 2, 4-dicinnamoyl resorcinol(Ia) which gave a dimethyl ether and colour reactions of a chalcone derivative. It was cyclised to the isomeric 2''-phenylflavono (7, 8:6'', 5'')-pyran-4''-one(IIa) by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. This on refluxing with palladium on charcoal in diphenyl ether gave 2''-phenylflavono (7, 8:6'', 5'') γ -pyrone(IIIa). The same product was obtained when the dicinnamoyl derivative was

refluxed with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol. Its structure was proved by a stepwise synthesis from the known 7-hydroxy-8-acetyl flavone³ by condensation with benzaldehyde and cyclodehydrogenation of the 8-cinnamoyl derivative obtained with selenium dioxide. Through a similar sequence of reactions 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol and anisaldehyde gave the corresponding 2''-(*p*-methoxyphenyl) derivative(IIIb). The Michael addition of diethyl malonate to the above dicinnamoyl derivatives gave the esters(IVa and b) which on hydrolysis and partial decarboxylation gave the dibasic acids(Va and b).

Ia, R=H
Ib, R=OCH₃

IIa, R=H
IIb, R=OCH₃

IIIa, R=H
IIIb, R=OCH₃

IVa, R=H
IVb, R=OCH₃

Va, R=H
Vb, R=OCH₃

Experimental

2, 4-Dicinnamoyl resorcinol: A mixture of 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol² (1 g) and benzaldehyde (2 ml) in alcohol (20 ml) was kept at room temperature for 24 hrs with potassium hydroxide solution (5 g

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in 5 ml water). The product obtained on dilution and acidification with hydrochloric acid was treated with sodium hydroxide solution. It was found to be completely soluble indicating that no cyclised product was present. The clear filtrate on acidification gave an orange product which was crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow beads (0.4 g), m.p. 128-130°. (Found: C, 77.61; H, 4.97. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4$ requires C 77.84; H, 4.87%). It gave a positive Wilson test and a deep red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid.

The Dimethyl ether: The above dicinnamoyl derivative (1 g) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (2 ml) in dry acetone (20 ml) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate on a steam bath for 6 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone and addition of water crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in pale yellow beads, m. p. 155° (Found: C, 78.22, H, 5.53. $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 78.39, H, 5.53%).

2''-Phenylflavono (7,8 : 6'',5'')-pyran-4''-one: 2, 4-Dicinnamoyl resorcinol (1 g) was refluxed with alcohol (50 ml) containing hydrochloric acid (5 ml) for 24 hr on a steam bath. The product obtained after dilution crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles, m. p. 200° (Found: C, 77.52; H, 4.97. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 77.84; H, 4.86%).

2''-Phenylflavono (7,8 : 6'',5'')-γ-pyrone: 2, 4-Dicinnamoyl resorcinol (1 g) was dissolved in dry iso-amyl alcohol (10 ml) and the solution refluxed with selenium dioxide (6 g) in an oil bath at 140-50° for 16 hr. It was filtered hot. The product obtained on cooling crystallised from xylene in long pale yellow needles, m. p. 280° (Found: C, 78.45; H, 3.68. $C_{24}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 78.68; H, 3.82%). The same product was obtained when (IIa) was refluxed in diphenyl ether with 10% palladium on charcoal for 12 hr.

7-Hydroxy 8-cinnamoyl flavone: To a mixture of 7-hydroxy 8-acetyl flavone^a (1 g) and benzaldehyde (2 ml) in alcohol (50 ml) potassium hydroxide (10 g in 10 ml water) was added. After keeping at room temperature for 24 hr it was acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow shining needles (0.6 g) m. p. 208°. It gave the usual colour reactions for a chalcone. (Found: C, 78.29; H, 4.34. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 78.26; H, 4.35%).

The acetyl derivative: 7-Hydroxy 8-cinnamoyl flavone (0.5 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (3 ml) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g) for 1 hr. The product separating after pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice crystallised from acetic acid in white shining needles, m. p. 138° (Found: C, 75.86; H, 4.22. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 76.09%; H, 4.39%).

Cyclodehydrogenation: 7-Hydroxy-8-cinnamoyl flavone (0.5 g) was refluxed in dry iso-amyl alcohol (10 ml) with selenium dioxide (2 g) for 16 hr in an oil bath at 140-50°. It was filtered hot. The product obtained on cooling crystallised from xylene in tiny yellow needles, m. p. 280°. Mixed m. p. with 2''-phenylflavono (7,8 : 6'',5'')-γ-pyrone described above was not depressed.

2,4-Di(p-Methoxy cinnamoyl) resorcinol: Prepared from 2, 4-diacetyl resorcinol (1 g) and anisaldehyde (2 ml) in alcohol (50 ml) and potassium hydroxide (5 g in 5 ml water) as before, crystallised from ethyl acetate in orange red needles (0.6 g) m.p. 156°. It gave positive tests for a chalcone. (Found C, 72.06; H, 4.95. $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 72.56, H, 5.12%).

The dimethyl ether: Prepared as usual from the above dicinnamoyl derivative and crystallised from benzene gave m. p. 120° (Found: C, 73.26; H, 5.73. $C_{28}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 73.33; H, 5.70%).

2''-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-4'-methoxyflavono (7,8 : 6'',5'')-pyran-4''-one: Obtained from the above dicinnamoyl resorcinol (1 g) by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid for 24 hr and crystallised from ethyl acetate gave m. p. 186° yield 0.4 g (Found: C, 72.92; H, 5.00. $C_{26}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 72.56; H, 5.12%).

2''-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-4'-methoxyflavono (7,8 : 6'',5'')-γ-pyrone: The above di-(p-methoxy cinnamoyl) resorcinol (1 g) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (6 g) in iso-amyl alcohol in an oil bath at 140-50° for 18 hr. It was filtered hot and the separated pale yellow product crystallised from xylene, m. p. 286°, yield 0.3 g (Found: C, 73.16; H, 4.18. $C_{26}H_{16}O_6$ requires, C, 73.24; H, 4.23%).

2,4-Bis[ω,β'(ethyl-α'-carbethoxy phenyl propionate) acetyl] resorcinol: To a mixture of 2,4-dicinnamoyl resorcinol (1 g) and diethyl malonate (10 ml) in alcohol (50 ml), sodium ethoxide solution (0.5 g sodium in 5 ml absolute alcohol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hr and then diluted with water. On acidification it afforded the ester which crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 128°, yield 0.8 g (Found: C, 65.68; H, 5.89. $C_{38}H_{42}O_{12}$ requires C, 66.10; H, 6.08%).

2, 4-Bis[ω, β'(phenylpropionic acid) acetyl] resorcinol: The above ester was kept overnight at room temperature with 10% sodium hydroxide solution. The product obtained on acidification was purified by taking in sodium bicarbonate solution and the alkaline solution was then acidified. The crude product (1 g) was heated in a dry test-tube in an oil bath at 180° till the effervescence ceased. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and acidified to get the dibasic acid. It

crystallised from alcohol. m.p. 188-89° (Found : C, 68.75; H, 5.63. $C_{28}H_{26}O_8$ requires C, 68.57; H, 5.31%).

2, 4-Bis[ω , β' (ethyl- α' -carbethoxy β' -p-methoxyphenyl propionate) acetyl] resorcinol : Prepared as before from 2, 4-di(p-methoxy cinnamoyl) resorcinol (1 g) and diethyl malonate (10 ml) in the presence of sodium ethoxide (0.5 g in 5 ml alcohol and crystallised from alcohol gave m. p. 115° (Found : C, 63.76; H, 5.94. $C_{40}H_{46}O_{14}$ requires C, 63.98; H, 6.13%).

2,4-Bis[ω , β' -(p-methoxyphenyl propionic acid) acetyl] resorcinol : Prepared from the above compound as before and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. 175° (Found : C, 64.29; H, 5.72. $C_{30}H_{30}O_{10}$ requires C, 64.45; H, 5.45%).

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LTA Cyclization of Some 2-benzothiazolyl Hydrazones

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SOME of the benzothiazole derivatives are well known fungicidal and bactericidal compounds.

Similarly s-triazoles are also known as physiologically active compounds¹. With the interest of preparing some compounds with a condensed system, Triazolobenzothiazoles, the work was undertaken. The most convenient well known procedure for preparing parent system was aza heterocyclic hydrazino compound treated with acidic cyclodehydrating agents for ring closure². For other compounds oxidative cyclization of hydrazones can be carried out.

In earlier studies, Leadtetraacetate was looked upon solely as a mean of cyclizing hydrazones. S-triazoloisoquinoline³, s-triazolobenzoxazoles⁴, s-triazolopyridine⁵ and s-triazolopyrazine⁶ were prepared by this method. Butler and Scott^{7,8} pointed out the existence of competitive acetoxylation process during LTA treatment. These authors reported that the products which Bower and Doyle⁹ considered as s-triazolobenzothiazole contained a molecule of acetic acid of solvation. Barton and Coworkers¹⁰ confirmed the same. Some of the hydrazones prepared in our laboratory were subjected to LTA oxidation. The reaction was carried out in acetic acid solvent. The crude product thus isolated refluxed with benzene. The benzene soluble and insoluble parts were separated. Benzene insoluble part could not be analysed since it was somewhat muddy and sticky in nature. Perhaps this may contain acetoxyated part. The soluble part was a cyclized compound. The same was confirmed by using Br_2 /acetic acid as cyclizing agent with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles. Compared to triazolobenzoxazoles cyclization is taking place without much difficulty may be perhaps due to more polarizable and less electronegative sulphur in the heterocyclic system. Our results are in agreement with Butler, Scott and Barton et al. The melting point and analytical data are in agreement with cyclized structures¹¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3-SUBSTITUTED-S-TRIAZOLO(3,4-b)-BENZOTHIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Substituent	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Solvent for crys.	Yield %	% N found
1.	Phenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3S$	185	benzene	48	16.84
2.	2'-hydroxyphenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3OS$	160	alcohol	56	15.80
3.	4'-hydroxyphenyl	$C_{14}H_9N_3OS$	165	alcohol	42	15.78
4.	2-Pyridyl	$C_{12}H_6N_4S$	232	benzene	50	22.24
5.	2-Thienyl	$C_{12}H_6N_3S_2$	145	benzene	52	16.14

Experimental

Benzothiazolyl hydrazones prepared by taking equimolar proportions of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole and required aldehyde in ethanol. The details were published¹².

Cyclization of 2-benzothiazolyl hydrazones to

(i) 3-Phenyl-s-triazolo(3,4-b)benzothiazole :

The 2-phenyl benzothiazolyl hydrazone (1.0 g) was taken in (8 ml) of glacial acetic acid. Leadtetraacetate (2.5 g) was added in portions to the above solution. The mixture was boiled for 20 minutes and then poured over cold water, it filtered. The residue was faint greenish colour. The crude ppt was taken in benzene refluxed for half an hour. The insoluble part was separated by filtration.